

**ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT
ON EVALUATION OF EMPLOYEE'S
PERFORMANCE IN PRIVATE SECTOR**

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Abstract

Performance management is one of the vital key activities performed to monitor the performance of their employees. Organizations must regularly evaluate the performance of their employees in order to understand their current and future abilities. The purpose of this paper is to assess the role of human resource management on employee and organizational performance. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design and involved a sample size of 30 human resource executives and employees from selected private organizations.

Data was collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive and the results presented using pie chart. The findings of the study reveal that private organizations practice performance management and have effective performance management system to appraise the enactment of their employees. Moreover, the findings reveal that there is a significant relationship between performance management and employee performance as well as between performance management and organizational performance. The study recommends the need of the private organizations to uphold and continue practicing and executing effective performance management system, also to continue assessing the performance of their employees frequently because it helps to determine training needs and at the same time acts as a motivational strategy hence leads to a better enactment of employees and organization.

Introduction

The research and the background will include the drawback statement research objectives and questions, and also the importance of the topic which is the influence of human resource management practices on employee's training and development, motivations, regarding and the relationship between HR practices and employee's performance, The influence of human resource management HRM, practices on employee's performance it's been stated

That there is progress on organizational performance. The way an organization manages people can influence its performance in such a particular HRM

practice employee's performance, training and development, motivating and regarding employees and also the implementation of HR policies on the performance of organization, Private Organization scan end in various ways to enhance HRM practices to mend employee skills as well as motivate them to work harder in achieving the vision, mission, objectives and goals targets of the organization. And taking into consideration because employee's not meeting their set targets by providing advance training and development. The main drawback is that why there is HRM discrepancy between policies and implementation. Human resource management HRM, practice could influence the behavior of individual or team of employees and the influence of HRM practices on employee's commitment and performance will depend on employee's perception and evaluation of these in practices. HRM practice policy must state exactly what must be done so that objective and goals of the organization and employees can perform their duties or task. It is important to know the relationship between HRM practice and employee's performance and the difference between them. To identify and examine the relationship between HR practices and employee's performance and identify human resource practices to build employee' performance.

Identifying the means to motivate and reward employees at work place to perform at work.

Background of the study

The problem is that the role of human resource management on evaluation of employee's performance, it is an important tool in every workplace and without employees no objective or goal can be achieved. So, it is important to ensure that employees are trained and developed at all the level in order to perform their set objective or goals to be achieved successfully. There must be ways in dealing with poor performance. What are the influences of HRM?

practices on employee's performance, what performance system or techniques can be used to ensure that employee's performance all the time is on high standards. If employee's performance is poor what can be done to ensure that employees can perform better.

Performance appraisal

Performance appraisal is introduced by the organization to review and evaluate the performance of employees over a certain period of time. Cumming (1972) established that the overall objective of performance appraisal is to improve the efficiency of an organization by attempting to mobilize the best possible efforts from individuals employed in it. Murphy (2004) stated that in many organizations, performance appraisals are expected to fulfill numerous functions including feedback, coaching, goal setting, skills development, pay determination, legal documentation, employee comparison and layoff selections.

Aforo & Antwi, (2012) postulated that performance appraisal system is comprised of setting goals, communicating feedback, participation and incentives for employee's performance. Fletcher

(2004) disclosed that performance appraisal remains the primary way of discussing and acting on the development of the individual. Brown et al. (2010) insisted that performance

appraisal is designed to stimulate employee performance as well as organizational performance. Performance evaluation is a systematic process of measuring a person's performance in the job, based on predetermined performance criteria (Clake, 2011) and it aligns itself to the organization strategies and provides a lively link to general and specific human resource functions (Vukotich, 2014). Robert (2002) narrated that the criteria for performance appraisal is to be participative from the employee's point of view. Parker et al (2013) pointed out that performance appraisal is a process of periodically reviewing one's performance against the various elements of the job.

An Effective Performance Appraisal-

- Uses specific objectives previously set with employees as standards to measure progress.
- Puts the employee at ease and explains the purpose of the feedback interview.
- Encourages and supports.
- Is clear about consequences if performance does not mend.
- Criticizes performance, not the person, when giving negative feedback.
- Obtains employee participation and encourages self-evaluation.
- Uses specific examples to support ratings.
- Has the employee summarized the feedback to ensure understanding?
- Creates a future plan of development jointly with the employee.

Methods of performance appraisal used by private organizations

- Ranking method
- Self-Appraisal
- Behavioral Assessment
- Peer and subordinate appraisal
- Appraisal by supervisor

Research Methodology

This study applied descriptive research design and only secondary sources have been used to collect the data from the research articles on the various research journals.

The study is based on data collected from primary source. A survey of 30 was conducted by me on human resource interventions. Respondents belonging to higher, middle, lower management were the sample for the study. The scope of survey was consisting of people engaged in management activity. Survey was conducted through close ended questionnaire based on mcq. The questionnaire comprised of various items about HR interventions and environmental factors affecting the organization i.e., leadership, training and development, job satisfaction, job rotation, goals and targets, work stress etc.

Research Design

The research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted. It constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement and analysis of data.

Data Approach	:	Questionnaire
Data Source	:	Primary
Persons involved in sample collection:		1
Sample Collection Time	:	1 month
Sample Size	:	30 Persons
Sample Unit	:	Male and Females under the age group of 22 to 40 above.
Research Type:		Descriptive

Conclusion and Recommendations

Many organizations in today competitive business environment rely on effective performance management system to evaluate the performance of their employees and to determine the position of the organization in terms of performance. The study found that private organizations have effective PMS in place to evaluate the performance of their employees.

Consequently, the study found that there is a significant relationship between human resource management, performance management and performance of employees and organization. Therefore, the study recommends that performance management

practices should be applicable to all employees in the organization.

Relatively, the study recommends a continuous review of PMS and HRM in order to keep them up to date. Furthermore, the study recommends regular meetings and feedback on performance appraisal outcomes. Moreover, the study recommends that there is a need of private organizations to start focusing on other remedial actions such as counselling and training once a poor performance is identified during appraisal instead of focusing much on imposing disciplinary actions as a remedial action. The organizations should utilize a variety of reward and recognition programs to drive behavior that promotes high performance. Organizations conduct extensive training programs for their employees relevant to the changing needs of jobs and business. Job performance should be considered an important factor to determine the compensation of employee's performance. Management should value the contribution and ideas shared by employees and empower employees to maximize their individual talent in order to make effective decisions. Similarly, the study recommends that private organizations should use the findings and recommendations of this study to improve and maintain effective PMS in the organizations. Finally, this study only centered and focused on private organizations.

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